

Perceived Safety And Bank Customers' Usage Of Self Service Technologies In Anambra State Of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of perceived safety on bank customers' usage of self service technologies (SST) in Anambra State of Nigeria. This study became necessary following the increased customer concerned about the security and reliability of these platforms in light of rising cases of electronic fraud, identity theft, ATM card skimming, phishing attacks, and unauthorized account access. Related conceptual, theoretical and empirical literatures were reviewed. Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology was adopted as the theoretical framework. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was the customers that use SSTs in Union Banks Plc and United Banks for African Plc. A sample of 382 respondents was determined using Cochran formula. Questionnaire was employed as the instrument of data collection. The data generated were analyzed using descriptive statistics and simple regression technique at 5% level of significance. The study found that perceived safety has significant effect on bank customers' usage of self service technologies in Anambra State. The study concludes that perceived safety had significant influence on bank customers' usage of self service technologies in Anambra State. The study recommends amongst others that banks should invest in advanced cybersecurity infrastructure to protect customers' financial information and transaction data in order to minimize the security risk inherent in the usage of these technologies.

Keywords: Perceived Safety, Self Service Technologies

INTRODUCTION

The global banking industry has undergone rapid transformation driven by technological innovations. One of the most prominent developments is the rise of self-service technologies (SSTs) - digital interfaces that enable customers to perform banking transactions independently without direct assistance from bank staff (Marfo, Owusu-Bio & Asamoah, 2021). These technologies include Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), Internet Banking, Mobile Banking Applications, Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD), Point of Sales (POS) Terminals, and Interactive Voice Response (IVR) system. The importance of self-service technology (SST) in service industry particularly in the banking sector cannot be overemphasized. Self-service technologies have increasingly become important in the service environment over the past decade. In fact, technology-based interactions are expected to become a crucial element for long-term success in service delivery in the service industry (Maune, 2022). They offer significant advantages such as convenience, 24/7 access, reduced transaction time, and decongestion of banking halls. In Nigeria, the Central Bank and commercial banks have actively promoted the use of SSTs in line with the cashless policy aimed at reducing the reliance on physical cash and promoting electronic payments. Particularly in Anambra, a highly urbanized and economically active state in southeastern Nigeria, there has been a marked increase in the deployment of these technologies by banks to cater to the diverse financial needs of individuals, businesses, and traders.

Banks joined the bandwagon of self-service technologies deployment as a way to improve their service delivery. Self service technologies are technological interfaces through which customers can attain services without the direct involvement of service firm employees (Ugwuanyi, Uduji & Oraedu, 2021). They noted that self-service technologies are technological interfaces that enable customers to produce a service outcome independent of direct service employee involvement. The emergence of this innovative way of service delivery has led to a considerable amount of changes in the way and manner services are delivered to customers; interactions between service providers/their personnel and customers have changed to interactions between technology and customers (Kim & Yang, 2018). Self service technologies are replacing many face-to-face service interactions with the intention to make service transactions more accurate, convenient, and faster (Foroudi, Gupta, Sivarajah & Broderick, 2018).

However, despite the perceived benefits of SSTs, the actual adoption and usage rate among customers vary significantly. Some customers adopt the technologies with ease, while others express hesitancy or complete avoidance. One of the most critical factors influencing this pattern is perceived safety. Customers are increasingly concerned about the security and reliability of these platforms in light of rising cases of electronic fraud, identity theft, ATM card skimming, phishing attacks, and unauthorized account access (Ezenwafor, Adeola & Ejiroghene, 2020). These safety concerns are not unfounded. Reports by regulatory bodies and financial institutions in Nigeria have highlighted a steady rise in cybersecurity breaches and fraud-related losses in the banking sector. These incidents have eroded customer trust and raised doubts about the ability of banks to safeguard users' data and funds during electronic transactions. In Anambra State, where a substantial proportion of the population is entrepreneurial and often handles large volumes of financial transactions, perceived safety plays a crucial role in determining whether customers will adopt or reject digital banking solutions.

Undoubtedly, a lot of contextual issues can create dissatisfaction with self service technologies and eventually make consumers avoid these technologies. For instance, in the Nigerian banking context, the increased online financial fraud, poor internet connectivity, customers' inflexibility and low computer literacy, as well as the lack of confidentiality of personal information are among factors that impede customers' adoption and continuous use of technology-based self-service (Ugwuanyi, Uduji & Oraedu, 2021). Some customers respond lukewarmly or unfavourably to self service technologies. Observably, some bank customers find it uneasy to navigate around some SST systems, consequently, relying more on the assistance of some more experienced users. This often affects service flow, experience and the need for confidentiality, as well as security.

Furthermore, the issue of digital literacy also intersects with perceived safety. Some customers, particularly those from older age groups or rural areas within the state, may not fully understand how these technologies work or how to protect themselves while using them. As a result, they may perceive SSTs as inherently risky or confusing, further dampening their willingness to use them. On the other hand, customers who perceive SSTs as safe and secure are more likely to engage with them frequently and recommend them to others (Nghu, 2020). Therefore, building trust and confidence in these platforms is essential not just for enhancing customer satisfaction but also for ensuring the long-term sustainability of digital banking. Based on the foregoing, the study investigated the effect of perceived safety on bank customers' usage of self service technologies in Anambra State of Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Self Service Technologies

The term 'self-service technologies' was first used by Meuter, Ostrom, Roundtree and Bitner (2000) who defined them as 'technological interfaces that enable customers to produce a service independent of direct service employee involvement'. This term and definition gained wide acceptance in subsequent research by other authors. The term 'self-service technologies (SSTs)' is used to refer to technological interfaces through which customers can derive service benefits without the active participation of the firm's personnel (Eoghan & Kathyrn, 2017). Self service technologies are technological interfaces through which customers can attain services without the direct involvement of service firm employees (Ugwuanyi,

Uduji & Oraedu, 2021). They noted that self-service technologies are technological interfaces that enable customers to produce a service outcome independent of direct service employee involvement. SST, according to Meuter *et al.* (2000), refers to technological interfaces enabling customers to produce a service that does not entail the direct service of the employee. This means that consumers are able to transact the business transactions without the involvement or interference of the service provider's staffs. Fate (2017) explained SST as a way for "customers to generate services by themselves without the help of employees of the service provider.

Ezenwafor, Okeke and Aghara (2020) defined self-service technology as devices and machines that are facilitated by information, communication and the internet and allow customers to perform some activities without the presence of an employee from the organization. They include ATMs, online banking, internet banking and Point of Purchase (POS) terminals. By deploying SST, service providers can deliver better quality products and convenient solutions to customers and thereby engender customers' satisfaction and loyalty (Giovanis, Assimakopoulos & Sarmaniotis, 2018). From the service providers' perspective, SSTs seek to improve service delivery in terms of accuracy, speed and personalisation. Iqbal, Hassan and Habibah (2018) noted that SSTs help to minimise operational costs while also increasing productivity. SSTs can also serve as a means of distinguishing a particular provider from a bunch of other competitors in the market (Kaushik, Agrawal & Rahman (2015). De Leon, Atienza and Susilo (2020) argue that SSTs are advantageous in standardising service delivery, as the mood and personal idiosyncrasies of the service provider that may impact the service delivery process are removed or minimised.

Perceived Safety

It refers to freedom from danger, risks or doubts that customer will feel while interacting with self-service technologies. As per the study by Parasuraman *et al.* (2005), security and privacy are most important factors in evaluating SST. Similarly-, customers tend to assess the SST as to what extent it reduces their stress and anxieties due to lack of control exerted over the information exchange through the SST (De Leon, Atienza & Susilo, 2020). Therefore, SST should be free of performance ambiguities in order for it to be perceived as a quality service environment. Perceived risk and uncertainty have a negative impact on the attitude of the consumers and evaluation of SSTs, therefore customers tend to evaluate the security of the system whenever they consume the service rendered over SST. In other words, there is an inclination on the part of consumer to evaluate the probability of improper usage of information exchange over SST. So, this plays a vital role in evaluating the quality of SST (Mark & Ki-hyun, 2011).

Also, according to Kim, Ferrin, and Rao (2007), users' perceived safety could as well be seen as their belief concerning uncertain negative potential results from the electronic transaction. Most authors made claim that within online retail setting, there exist two predominant types of safety issues namely privacy risk and security risk (Giovanis, Assimakopoulos & Sarmaniotis, 2018). Talking about security risk, Bart *et al.* (2005) asserts that this could be seen as one of the factors that influences consumers trust when it comes to retailing in an online setting and the security which the online retailer provides talks about the safety of the financial information, credit card or computer. And in the case of privacy, Goodwin (1991 as cited in Ling *et al.*, 2011) defined it as the users' capability to manage and take charge of the sharing of information given during the time of the online transaction and also his ability checkmate the presence of others during the period of the transaction online (Fate, 2017).

The way an individual understands and perceives safety of using a given product or services is very crucial to organizations since it will enable them determine the psychological feelings the market has towards their offerings and make amendments where necessary (Khalufi & Shah, 2022). If the management of deposit money banks in Nigeria guarantees and assures skeptic customers of how safe and low risk it is to adopt the use of SST such as ATM and mobile banking apps as against their believe of it being risky and easy to hack by online fraudsters. This will help reduce their fears and will encourage them to perceive the products as low risk and safe to use (Liyang, 2016).

Theoretical Framework

This work is anchored on unified theory of acceptance and use of technology 2. The unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) 2 was developed by Venkatesh et al. (2012) as an extension of the original model Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology. In contrast to the previous technology acceptance models, UTAUT2 used additional exogenous constructs “habit”, “hedonic motivation” and “price value” to predict the endogenous construct “behavioral intention”, which is understood as an expression of technology acceptance. UTAUT 2 postulates that the use of technology by individuals is underpinned by the effect of the three additional constructs, namely, hedonic motive, cost/perceived value and habit, moderated by age, gender and experience. The theory additionally includes factors relevant for the consumer market that influence the behavioural intention to use new technology. The original and additional constructs are explained below in figure 2.

Figure 1: Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2

Source: Venkatesh, V., Thong, J. Y., & Xu, X. (2012).

Performance Expectancy: It is defined as the degree to which an individual believes that using the system will help him or her to attain gains in job performance. Performance expectancy is based on the constructs from Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), TAM2, Combined TAM and the Theory of Planned Behaviour (CTAMTPB), Motivational Model (MM), the model of PC utilisation (MPCU), Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT) and Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) (i.e. perceived usefulness, extrinsic motivation, job-fit, relative advantage and outcome expectations). It is the strongest predictor of use intention and is significant in both voluntary and mandatory settings.

Effort Expectancy: It is defined as the degree of ease associated with the use of the system. Effort Expectancy is constructed from perceived ease of use and complexity driven from TAM, MPCU, IDT, which share a similarity in definitions and scales. The effect of the construct becomes non significant after extended usage of technology.

Social Influence: It is defined as the degree to which an individual perceives that important others believe he or she should use the new system. Social influence is similar to the subjective norms, social factors and image constructs used in TRA, TAM2, TPB, CTAMTPB, MPCU, IDT in the way that they denote that the behaviour of people is adjusted to the perception of others about them. The effect of social influence is significant when the use of technology is mandated. In the mandatory context, individuals might use technology due to compliance requirement, but not personal preferences.

Facilitating Conditions: This is defined as the degree to which an individual believes that an organisation's and technical infrastructure exists to support the use of the system. The facilitating conditions construct is formed from compatibility, perceived behavioural control and facilitating conditions constructs drawn from TPB, CTAMTPB, MPCU and IDT. Facilitating conditions have a direct

positive effect on intention to use, but after initial use, the effect becomes non significant. Therefore, the model proposes that facilitating conditions have a direct significant effect on use behaviour.

Hedonic Motivation: Hedonic motivation is defined as the fun or pleasure derived from using a technology, and it has been shown to play an important role in determining technology acceptance and use. Hedonic motivation can influence technology acceptance and use directly. In the consumer context, hedonic motivation has also been found to be an important determinant of technology acceptance and use.

Price Value: An important difference between a consumer use setting and the organizational use setting, where UTAUT was developed, is that consumers usually bear the monetary cost of such use whereas employees do not. The cost and pricing structure may have a significant impact on consumers' technology use. Price value is the consumers' cognitive tradeoff between the perceived benefits of the applications and the monetary cost for using them. The price value is positive when the benefits of using a technology are perceived to be greater than the monetary cost and such price value has a positive impact on intention

Habit: Habit has been defined as the extent to which people tend to perform behaviors automatically because of learning. Habit has been operationalized in two distinct ways: first, habit is viewed as prior behavior; and second, habit is measured as the extent to which an individual believes the behavior to be automatic. Consequently, there are at least two key distinctions between experience and habit. One distinction is that experience is a necessary but not sufficient condition for the formation of habit. A second distinction is that the passage of chronological time (i.e., experience) can result in the formation of differing levels of habit depending on the extent of interaction and familiarity that is developed with a target technology.

This theory was adopted for this study in that it examines the acceptance of technology, determined by the effects of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, hedonic motivation, price value and habit. The theory provides insight into technology acceptance by comparing prominent technology acceptance theories, which often offer competing or partial perspectives on the subject. UTAUT2 demonstrates that the variance in use intention, offering stronger predictive power compared to the rest of the models that examine technology acceptance. The interactive effect of some constructs with personal and demographic factors demonstrates the complexity of the technology acceptance process, which is dependent on individuals' age, gender and experience.

Perceived Safety and Bank Customers' Usage of Self Service Technologies

Safety and security have been found to include some concerns new technologies adopters. For instance, insecurity has been defined as the distrust and skepticism of the banking customers in the performance of the SSTs for meeting their banking requirements and discomfort as the apprehension of loss of control over technology in TRI. Although discomfort and insecurity have been distinctly conceptualized in TRI, the items framed by Parasuraman (2000) for measuring these two constructs have been found to share some common characteristics—for instance, "Many new technologies have health or safety risks that are not discovered until people have used them" (p. 312) measuring discomfort and "You do not consider it safe to do any kind of financial business online" (p. 312) measuring insecurity. Both these measures include safety concern involved in adopting new technologies. Adding more, the items framed to assess discomfort were found to include environmental factors that are not customer specific like "Technical support lines are not helpful because they do not explain things in terms you understand" (p. 312) and "There is no such thing as manual for a high-tech product or service that's written in plain language" (p. 312). This also indicates the need to analyze these constructs before utilizing them for analyzing technology adoption behavior of the customers.

The important role of perceived safety could relate to the particular and sensitive nature of the banking industry in general, as well as online banking technology in particular, which is universally characterized by high uncertainty, intangibility, heterogeneity, and vagueness, along with the absence of human interaction (Kesharwani & Bisht, 2012). These characteristics make customers more apprehensive to use online banking, thereby mitigating their intentions to use this technology (Jaruwachirathanakul & Fink, 2005). In addition, customers seem to be more sensitive when it comes to financial matters, which

explains the crucial role of perceived risk in hindering customers' willingness to accept online banking channels (Im, Kim & Han 2008). Importantly, customers raise concerns that using SSTs exposes their bank account details to financial, fraud, and hacking risks, especially these related to banking.

Empirical Review

Marfo, Owusu-Bio and Asamoah (2018) carried out a study on the effect of self-service technologies on customer experiences in banking with particular reference to Ghana. Perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, perceived convenience, perceived security, computer self-efficacy, perceived credibility, mobile applications, web applications, USSD applications and ATM usage were employed as the independent variables while customer experience was employed as the dependent variable. The study adopted survey research design and a sample of 384 bank customers in Ghana were studied. Descriptive statistics and Partial Least Squares (PLS) was employed in analyzing the data. The result indicates that self-service technologies adoption have positive effect on customer experiences in Ghana banking industry. The study establishes that customers' adoption of self-service technologies is influenced by their perception of self-service technologies usefulness and ease of use, which increases their satisfaction level. The study found that when self-service technologies are deployed individually, they have no effect on customer experiences in the banking sector. However, when the individual self-service technologies are combined in usage, they collectively produce a positive effect on customer banking experience.

Obermeier, Jlingersberger and Auinger (2022) carried out a study on the factors influencing usage intentions towards a self-service kiosk with biometric authentication. In this study, functionality, convenience, relative advantage and security concerns were employed as the explanatory variables while intentions towards the self-service kiosk was employed as the dependent variable. Descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis were employed in analyzing the data. The findings revealed that convenience and relative advantage had a strong impact on usage intention. In contrast, functionality and security concerns towards biometric authentication showed no significant effects. In addition, the results indicate that usage intention affected positive word of mouth.

Nwachukwu, Azuonwu, Nwador, Dike and Origbo (2023) examined self-service technology adoption and post-purchase intentions of deposit money banks customers in Port Harcourt. Banks' mobile app and ATM card perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived low risk were employed as the independent variables while post-purchase intentions was applied as the dependent variable. The study adopted survey research design and a total of 189 postgraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt were sampled for the study. Pearson's moment correlation coefficient was used to analyze the data. The result indicates that the three dimensions of self-service technology adoption studied (perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived low risk) were critical in determining the outcome of post purchase intention.

Konan (2021) carried out a study on the determinants of mobile banking adoption with particular reference to Ecobank Togo specifically Lomé town. Perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, social trend, customer support and perceived risk were employed as the independent variables while mobile banking adoption was employed as the dependent variables. The study adopted survey research design. A total of 1422 respondents were sampled for the study. Descriptive statistics and simple regression analysis were employed in analyzing the data. The study found that ease of use, perceived risk and perceived usefulness are significant determinants of mobile banking adoption in Lome.

Ezenwafor, Adeola and Ejiroghene (2020) carried out a study on self service technology and customer satisfaction in the Nigerian online sport betting industry. Ease of use, reliability, security and website design were employed as the independent variable while customer satisfaction was employed as the dependent. The study adopted survey research design and a total of 236 respondents were employed in analyzing the data. Multiple regression analysis was employed in analyzing the data. The finding revealed that accessibility, security and website design have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction while reliability showed a positive but non-significant relationship amongst online bettors in Anambra state.

Nghi (2020) carried out a study on determinants of customer intentions to use self-service technology-based options for recoveries. Perceived control, perceived risk, efficiency and positive anticipated emotions were employed as the explanatory variables while customer intentions were employed as the dependent variable. The study adopted survey research design. Partial least squares structural equation modeling was employed in analyzing the data. The result indicates that perceived control, risk, efficiency and positive emotions have a direct impact on customer intentions towards using SST-based recovery. Perceived risk, efficiency, and positive emotions demonstrate mediating effects on the relationship between perceived control and intentions towards using SST-based recovery.

Fate (2017) carried out a study on the impact of technology based self service banking service quality on customer satisfaction in the Nigerian banking sector. The study focused five selected banks within Yola metropolis, in Adamawa state. The research determines the degree of impact of speed of delivery, convenience, efficiency, reliability and security as well as their influence on customer satisfaction. The study adopted survey research design and a total of 248 respondents were sampled for the study. Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) was employed in analyzing the data. The findings indicate that speed of delivery and reliability has significant influence on customer satisfaction. Speed of delivery, convenience and efficiency has small impact on customer satisfaction while reliability seen as having medium degree of impact on customer satisfaction, while security has a large impact on the customer satisfaction.

Waleed, Busra and Oya (2017) carried out an investigation into self-service technology (SST) of participation banking in Turkey. Functionality, enjoyment, security, assurance, design, convenience, and customization were employed as the explanatory variables while customer satisfaction and customer loyalty was employed as the dependent variables. The study adopted survey research design and a total of 165 customers of Kuveyt Turk in Turkey were sampled for the study using online survey. Structural equation modelling (SEM) was employed in analyzing the data. The result indicates that functionality, enjoyment, security, assurance, design, convenience, and customization positively affects customer satisfaction and customer loyalty; customer satisfaction influences customer loyalty; customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between SSTQAUL and customer loyalty.

Gap in Literature

Over the past two decades, numerous studies have explored the adoption and usage of self-service technologies (SSTs) in the banking sector, especially within the contexts of developing and emerging economies. Much of this research has focused on technology acceptance models (TAM), perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, customer satisfaction and service quality as key determinants of SST adoption. While these studies have provided valuable insights into user behavior, there is a noticeable gap in the literature regarding the specific role of perceived safety, particularly in regions experiencing a surge in electronic fraud and cyber threats like Nigeria. Also, there is a lack of localized studies that focus on customer perceptions in specific states such as Anambra, which has unique socioeconomic dynamics, including a large informal sector, active commercial hubs, and varying levels of digital literacy. The diversity within Anambra State—including urban centers like Awka and Onitsha as well as rural communities—demands a more nuanced, region-specific understanding of how safety concerns affect SST usage. Moreover, most existing studies treat safety concerns as a secondary variable, often subsumed under broader constructs like "trust" or "risk perception." There is a need for research that specifically isolates perceived safety as a core construct.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive research design using a survey method. This method was chosen because it is designed to scientifically describe phenomena and their relationships in the actual environment after a given time. This study was carried out in Anambra State, South East Nigeria. The state was selected because of its commercial and industrial nature which encourages high usage of self service technologies in banks. Customers of two banks in the state namely Union Banks Plc and United Banks for African Plc in Nnewi, Awka and Onitsha were studied. The population consists of the customers that use SSTs among

the two selected commercial banks in Anambra State. Cochran formula was employed to determine a sample size of 384. Primary data were sourced for this study. Questionnaire was employed as the instrument of data collection. The data that were generated through the questionnaire were analyzed using frequency tables and percentages, while the hypotheses formulated were tested using simple regression technique.

RESULTS

The first section covered the demographic features of the respondents followed by the analysis of the questionnaire. Furthermore, the hypotheses earlier formulated were empirically tested using simple regression analysis.

Demographic Features of the Respondents

In this section, the demographic features of the respondents were analyzed.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	Category	Frequencies	Percentage
Gender	Male	214	60.5
	Female	140	39.5
	Total	354	100
Age	18 – 30 Years	167	47.2
	31 – 40 Years	91	25.7
	41 – 50 Years	62	17.5
	51 Years and above	34	9.6
	Total	354	100
Marital Status	Single	164	46.3
	Married	168	47.5
	Others	22	6.2
	Total	354	100
Educational Qualification	O’Level	37	10.5
	OND/NCE	152	42.9
	B.Sc./HND	149	42.1
	M.Sc./MBA	6	1.7
	Ph.D	10	2.8
	Total	354	100
Number of Years with Bank	0 – 5 Years	59	16.7
	6 – 10 Years	178	50.3
	11 – 15 Years	83	23.4
	16 years and above	34	9.6
	Total	354	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 above depicts the gender distribution of the respondents. The table indicates that majority of the respondents numbering 214(60.5%) are male while the remaining 140 respondents accounting for 39.5% are female. This indicates that there are more male customers than female customers in the sampled banks in Anambra state.

The table above also measured the age distribution of the respondents. The table indicates that majority of the respondents accounting for 47.2% falls within the age bracket 18 to 30 years, 25.7% of the respondents fall within the age bracket of 31 to 40 years, 17.5% falls within the age bracket of 41 to 50 years while the remaining 9.6% falls within the age bracket of 51 years and above. This indicates that

majority of the respondents falls within the age bracket of 18 – 30 years implying that majority of the respondents are young.

Table 1 also assessed the marital status of the customers of the sampled banks in Anambra state. The table indicates that 164 respondents accounting for 46.3% of the total respondents were single, 168 respondents accounting for 47.5% were married while the remaining 22 respondents accounting for 6.2% were either divorced or widowed.

Table 1 further shows that majority of the respondents accounting for 10.5% had O’level as their educational qualification, 42.9% of the respondents has either OND or NCE as their educational qualification, 42.1% of the respondents had either B.Sc. or HND as their educational qualification, 1.7% had either M.Sc. or MBA as their educational qualification while the remaining 2.8 had PhD/others as their educational qualification. This implies that majority of the respondents are enlighten.

Table 1 above indicates that majority of the respondents accounting for 50.3% agreed that they have been banking with the bank between 6 to 10 years, 16.7% of the respondents have been with the bank for between 0 to 5 years, 23.4% of the respondents have been with the bank for between 11 to 15 years while the remaining 9.6% of the respondents have been with the bank for 16 years and above.

Table 2 Analysis of Questionnaire Items Related to Perceived Safety and Customer Usage of Service Technology

s/n	Items	SA	A	D	SD
1	Using self service technology in banks may give me a feeling of anxiety	64 (18.1%)	235 (66.4%)	41 (11.5%)	14 (4%)
2	I obtain accurate and error free service from my bank’s SST	109 (30.8%)	153 (43.2%)	66 (18.6%)	26 (5.9%)
3	Risk associated with my bank’s SST is low	89 (25.1%)	201 (56.8%)	39 (11%)	25 (7.1%)
4	Personal information exchanged over SST is not misused by bank	77 (21.8%)	215 (60.7%)	34 (9.6%)	28 (7.9%)
5	I think there is a significant chance that my personal information can be lost when I use self service technology in banks	132 (37.3%)	142 (40.1%)	56 (15.8%)	24 (6.8%)
6	I sometimes wonder if it is safe to use self service technology in banks	157 (44.4%)	154 (43.5%)	19 (5.4%)	24 (6.8%)
8	The ease in use of self service technologies encourages to use it	103 (29.1%)	186 (52.5%)	39 (11%)	26 (7.4%)
9	The level of safety encourages me to use of self service technologies	141 (39.8%)	90 (25.4%)	98 (27.7%)	25 (7.1%)
10	Perceived level of trust influences my usage of self service technologies	140 (39.5%)	121 (34.2%)	53 (15%)	40 (11.3%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above indicates that 64 respondents accounting for 18.1% strongly agreed that using self service technology in banks may give them a feeling of anxiety, 235 respondents accounting for 66.4% agreed, 41 respondents accounting for 11.5% disagreed while 14 respondents accounting for 4% strongly disagreed. This implies that using self service technology in banks may give customers a feeling of anxiety.

The table above indicates that 109 respondents accounting for 30.8% strongly agreed that they obtain accurate and error free service from their bank’s SST, 153 respondents accounting for 43.2% agreed, 66 respondents accounting for 18.6% disagreed while 26 respondents accounting for 5.9% strongly disagreed. This implies that customers obtain accurate and error free service from their bank’s SST.

The table above indicates that 89 respondents accounting for 25.1% strongly agreed that risk associated with their bank’s SST is low, 201 respondents accounting for 56.8% agreed, 39 respondents accounting

for 11% disagreed while 25 respondents accounting for 7.1% strongly disagreed. This implies that risk associated with bank's SST is low.

The table above indicates that 77 respondents accounting for 21.8% strongly agreed that personal information exchanged over SST is not misused by bank, 215 respondents accounting for 60.7% agreed, 24 respondents accounting for 9.6% disagreed while 28 respondents accounting for 7.9% strongly disagreed. This implies that personal information exchanged over SST is not misused by bank.

The table above indicates that 132 respondents accounting for 37.3% strongly agreed that there is a significant chance that their personal information can be lost when they use self service technology in banks, 142 respondents accounting for 40.1% agreed, 56 respondents accounting for 15.8% disagreed while 24 respondents accounting for 6.8% strongly disagreed. This implies that there is a significant chance that customers personal information can be lost when they use self service technology in banks.

The table above indicates that 157 respondents accounting for 44.4% strongly agreed that they sometimes wonder if it is safe to use self service technology in banks, 154 respondents accounting for 43.5% agreed, 19 respondents accounting for 5.4% disagreed while 24 respondents accounting for 6.8% strongly disagreed. This implies that customers sometimes wonder if it is safe to use self service technology in banks.

The table above indicates that 103 respondents accounting for 29.1% strongly agreed that the ease in use of self service technologies encourages to use it, 186 respondents accounting for 52.5% agreed, 39 respondents accounting for 11% disagreed while 26 respondents accounting for 7.4% strongly disagreed. This implies that the ease in use of self service technologies encourages to use it.

The table above indicates that 141 respondents accounting for 39.8% strongly agreed that the level of safety encourages them to use of self service technologies, 90 respondents accounting for 25.4% agreed, 98 respondents accounting for 27.7% disagreed while 25 respondents accounting for 7.1% strongly disagreed. This implies that the level of safety encourages customers to use of self service technologies.

The table above indicates that 140 respondents accounting for 39.5% strongly agreed that perceived level of trust influences their usage of self service technologies, 121 respondents accounting for 34.2% agreed, 53 respondents accounting for 15% disagreed while 40 respondents accounting for 11.3% strongly disagreed. This implies that perceived level of trust influences their usage of self service technologies.

Regression Results

The regression results are presented in the tables below.

Table 2: Summary of Regression Result

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.840 ^a	.706	.703	1.867	1.904

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Safety

b. Dependent Variable: Customer Usage of Self Service Technologies

Source: SPSS Version 21

The table above shows that summary of the regression result. The R square (R²) value of 0.706 indicates that 70.6 percent of the variations in customer usage of self service technologies are explained by variations in perceived safety. Similarly, R square adjusted value of 0.703 indicates that 70.3% of variation in the dependent variable is accounted by variation in the independent variable, all things been equal. The Durbin-Watson statistics which is employed to check for autocorrelation recorded 1.904 as its value which is within the acceptable threshold. This shows that the variables used in the model are not auto-correlated and are therefore, reliable for predications.

Table 3: ANOVA Result

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4704.657	5	940.931	269.822	.000 ^a
	Residual	1959.822	562	3.487		
	Total	6664.479	567			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Safety

b. Dependent Variable: Customer Usage of Self Service Technologies

Source: SPSS Version 21

Table 3 above indicates that the F-test which test the overall significance of the model recorded a value of 269.822 with a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significant. This indicates that perceived safety explain the variations in customer usage of self service technologies. This indicates that perceived safety influences customer usage of self service technologies in Anambra State.

Table 4. Coefficients of the Multiple Regression Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	13.024	1.149		11.335	.000
Perceived Safety	.177	.042	.316	4.170	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Usage of Self Service Technologies

Source: SPSS Version 21

Perceived safety has a t-statistics value of 4.170 with an alpha value of 0.000 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This implies that perceived safety significantly influence bank customers' usage of self service technologies in Anambra State.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that perceived safety significantly influence bank customers' usage of self service technologies in Anambra State. This implies that the safety of self service technologies influences customer's usage of the platform. This is in line with the findings of Konan (2021) that perceived risk is a determinant of mobile banking adoption. This agrees with the findings of Marfo, Owusu-Bio and Asamoah (2021) that customers' adoption of SSTs is influenced by security of self service technologies. Similarly, Ezenwafor, Adeola and Ejiroghene (2020) found that security influences customer satisfaction with self service technologies.

The adoption of self-service technologies (SSTs) in the banking sector has transformed how customers interact with financial institutions, offering greater convenience, speed, and accessibility. However, the effectiveness and widespread use of these technologies depend largely on how customers perceive their safety. In Anambra State, where economic activity is vibrant and diverse, the issue of perceived safety plays a significant role in influencing customers' willingness to adopt and consistently use SSTs such as ATMs, mobile banking, internet banking, and POS systems. Despite ongoing efforts by banks and regulators to promote digital banking and enhance cybersecurity, customer concerns about fraud, identity theft, system errors, and lack of recourse remain prevalent. These concerns often translate into low adoption rates, underutilization of SSTs, or complete avoidance by certain segments of the population. This study underscores the importance of addressing perceived safety not just as a technical issue, but as a critical behavioral and psychological factor that shapes customer trust and confidence.

The study recommends that banks should invest in advanced cybersecurity infrastructure to protect customers' financial information and transaction data. This includes stronger authentication systems (e.g., biometric verification, two-factor authentication), encryption of customer data, and continuous system monitoring to detect and respond to security threats in real-time. Banks should invest in advanced cybersecurity infrastructure to protect customers' financial information and transaction data. This includes stronger authentication systems (e.g., biometric verification, two-factor authentication), encryption of customer data, and continuous system monitoring to detect and respond to security threats in real-time.

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